

Learning with Web Technologies after Pandemic Situation: Educational Technology

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Abstract:- Although the Web community should not yet be fully accepting of the emerging technology, acceptance should be growing over time. Its level of acceptance may be modest, but if it stays that way continuously and doesn't increase, it won't be deemed to be emerging. Its level of acceptance can also be high, but if it is extremely high, it would be seen as a pre-existing innovation and would no longer be developing, even if its fame is constantly growing. Therefore, it is wise to keep updating the list of developments that could potentially emerge. The level of acceptance of emerging web innovations in academic settings is rising. These advances include online resources like wikis and websites. A blog is a type of website that is typically updated by an individual and has standard portions of conversation, representation of events, or other content like artwork or video. A Wikipedia is a collection of interconnected Web pages that reflect the collaborative efforts of numerous authors, creators

Keywords:- Online learning, web technologies, education, pandemic situation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Schools were closed and classes were moved to students' home in 2020 as the Covid-19 pandemic spread over the world. As a result, several countries faced the challenge of an unplanned and accelerated shift to online learning. This addresses a crucial opportunity to consider innovation, instructional strategy, and education. Computerized technology played a significant role in enabling teachers to show students the right path by using tools that enabled both simultaneous and nonconcurrent communication with the entire class, groups, and specific children or youngsters; access to learning materials; and intuitive and cooperative exercises. This particular issue examines how patients responded as a whole, the questions and insights that emerged, and what we may learn about moving forward with modern training innovation in times of crisis. While different countries are at different stages of the covid-19 epidemic, as of right now, more than one billion children in more than 150 countries have been affected by institution closures due to the covid lockdown.

Some people have serious concerns about whether web-based learning platforms will continue to be used after the current epidemic and what this might mean for the overall tutoring market due to the unexpected shift in study and learning habits from classroom halls to homes in many parts of society and the world.

A. How is the education division reacting to pandemic situation?

Numerous web-based learning platforms, including UNACADEMY, LETS LEARN, and BYJU, India's largest ed-tech business and the maker of the country's most popular school learning software, are no longer granting admission to their administrations due to high demand. BYJU'S, a 2015 startup, provides classes 1 through 12 with highly individualized and successful learning programmes (K-12). Different organizations are reinforcing capacities to give an all in one resource to educators and understudies. For instance, Lark, a Singapore-based joint effort suite at first created by Byte Dance as an inner instrument to meet its own outstanding development, started offering instructors and understudies limitless video conferencing time, auto-interpretation capacities, ongoing co-altering of task work, and shrewd schedule planning, among different elements. To do so rapidly and in a period of emergency, Lark sloped up its worldwide server framework and designing capacities to guarantee dependable network.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study how educational institutions are reacting to pandemic situations?
- To identify the various educational opportunities during pandemic of COVID-19.
- To identify the online learning obstacles.
- To study some best practices to educate with web technologies.

III. METHODS

- **Secondary Data:** Data have been taken from an organization and a published source (Table.1. EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY AND EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITY DURING COVID-19 SCHOOL CLOSURES: A CASE STUDY OF CHENNAI, TAMIL NADU), (Fig.1, Fig.2, Fig.3, Source: February 2021 Brookings phone surveys.
- **Unstructured Data:** Interviews with the school and college students.
- **Descriptive Research Method.**
- **References from various books and research paper.**

IV. REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE:

Learning conditions and technologies: The success of online learning for students depends on them having consistent internet access. Berge (2005) voiced concern about the gap in digital readiness and how different countries' pedagogical approaches can affect students' online learning. The acceptance and availability of information technologies and infrastructures in a nation is referred to as its level of digital readiness. In terms of digital preparedness, Western nations like the United States (3rd) performed substantially better than Asian nations like China (54th; Cisco, 2019). Students from nations with low levels of digital readiness may have additional issues with technology. Recent investigations carried out during the COVID-19 epidemic are providing supporting evidence. Basuony et al. (2020) discovered that just about 13.9 percent of the pupils in the nation's capital had problems with their internet connection. Whereas in rural Indonesia, more than two-thirds of students cited problems with erratic internet, insufficient internet data, and incompatible learning devices (Agung et al., 2020).

The availability of suitable technological tools, especially having access to a desktop or laptop, is another important consideration for K–12 children to successfully adjust to online learning (Barbour et al., 2018). The majority of pupils are unlikely to meet this standard. Even in higher education, only 15% of students utilised laptops for online learning while 85% of them used smartphones. Around 76% of students reported having incompatible devices for online learning (Agung et al., 2020). Given that K–12 kids rely on their parents to give access to appropriate learning equipment, it is extremely likely that they also experience this availability difficulty.

The use of electronic equipment by pupils may also be impacted by technical difficulties. According to (Barbour & Reeves, 2009), students must possess a high degree of digital literacy in order to locate and utilise pertinent information and interact with people online. Online learning could be challenging for students who lack such skill. According to Bczek et al. (2021), 54 percent of medical students encountered technical issues with IT equipment, and this problem was more common among students who had less university education. In a similar vein, Niemi and Kousa (2020) discover that students in a Finnish high school encountered more technological issues during the exam time that required more technical applications. These results are alarming since young kids and teenagers in elementary and lower secondary schools can be more vulnerable to these technological issues because they are less familiar with the technologies used in online learning (Barbour & LaBonte, 2017). Investigating the learning environments and related challenges faced by children in K–12 school is key because it is often unknown how much of an influence they have.

V. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

We found that the online learning experiences of primary and secondary school pupils during the COVID-19 pandemic varied between academic years. A number of suggestions were offered for the future application and study of online education among K–12 and secondary level students. First, educational institutions should choose online learning platforms that have been optimised for smartphones and should offer appropriate technical support to aid students in resolving any potential internet and technical issues. Second, tailoring the online pedagogy design for students in various school years, with a focus on giving young children enough guidance, giving older children and teenagers more online collaborative opportunities, and giving senior students who are preparing for final exams additional learning resources.

VI. SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS:

As Table 1 shows, our final sample included 201 households and 271 primary-school aged children. The ages of children in the sample ranged from 4 to 11 years. Only one child in our sample had never been enrolled in school, and five children were not enrolled in school during COVID-19 but had been enrolled prior to the onset of the pandemic. Because we were interested in understanding students' educational experiences before and during COVID-19, we excluded from our analysis the child who had never been enrolled in school.

Table 1 shows that our sample is evenly divided by SES, with approximately 50% of children in low-income households and another 50% from high-income households. For close to three-fourths (74%) of children in our sample, the mother serves as the primary caregiver, followed by the father, who serves as primary caregiver for nearly one-quarter (23%) of children. By gender, our sample has slightly higher representation of girls (52%) than boys (48%). In the analyses that follow, we only report differences by gender, type of school, and/or household SES when they are statistically significant.

VII. EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY AND EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITY DURING COVID-19 SCHOOL CLOSURES: A CASE STUDY OF CHENNAI, TAMIL NADU

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
• Gender of the Child		
Male	130	48.0
Female	141	52.0
Total	271	100.0
• Current enrolment status		
Enrolled	265	97.4
Not enrolled	6	2.6
Total	271	100.0
• Type of school		
Government	88	32.5
Private	182	67.2
Child never enrolled	1	0.4
Total	271	100.0

- **Medium of instruction**

English	230	84.9
Tamil	39	14.4
Malayalam	1	0.4
Child never enrolled	1	0.4
Total	271	100.0
- **Socioeconomic status of households**

Low	101	50.2
High	100	49.8
Total	201	100.0
- **Primary caregiver**

Mother	148	73.6
Father	47	23.4
Aunt	2	1.0
Grandmother	3	1.5
Sister	1	0.5
Total	201	100.0

Table 1: Summary of key variables

Movement of children by monetary establishment across government and non-public schools Prior to COVID-19, youths from low-pay establishments were likewise inclined to go to private or government schools. Be that as it may, their mates from significant association pay establishments were altogether more inclined to go to non-state funded schools. As Figure 1 shows, the degree of children from low-SES families in both sort of schools isn't very extraordinary. Oddly, only 14.4% of children from high-SES families were pursued government schools, while 85.6% of youths from these families were pursued private schools.

Fig. 1: School enrolment prior to COVID-19, by type of school and household income

Source: February 2021 Brookings phone surveys.

Government-funded and -managed schools are categorized into two categories in India: ordinary government schools and government-aided, privately managed institutions. We looked at how many kids go to private schools that get government financing against how many kids go to private schools that don't. The bulk of the students in our sample (67%) went to private schools that did not get any government support, whereas just 26% went to conventional government schools and 7% went to private schools that received government assistance.

A. Due to the COVID-19 school closures, educational technology was used:

Prior to COVID-19, there were restrictions on the use of computers, workstations, and tablets in homerooms. Only 8% of students reported using advanced devices daily or nearly daily, 15% reported using them several times per week, 14% reported using them at least once per week, and 3% reported using them around once per month, according to the respondents. In response to our example, respondents stated that 59 percent of students occasionally or never used computers in their classrooms. Both students in public and private schools were given the same example, but students in non-public schools consistently used educational technology more than their classmates in public schools.

As Figure 2 shows, 72% of students in government schools used digital devices rarely or never compared to 53% of students in private schools who used them rarely or never.

Fig. 2

Before the COVID-19 school shutdown, students rarely used educational technology outside of classroom teaching to complete homework assignments and participate in classroom activities. None of the 270 students in our example were given a PC/netbook, mobile phone, or tablet so they could learn at home. By and by, prior to COVID-19, about 14% of children used educational websites or platforms (such as YouTube or Google) before or after school (See Figure 3). In any case, 89% of children enrolled in government schools occasionally or never used websites or programming, and 85% of children attending private schools did the same. Prior to the COVID-19 school closures, admission to instructional locations or phases was not affected by family income or orientation.

Fig. 3

B. The obstacles of online learning:

Surviving is, in any case, challenging. Some students who lack reliable internet access or other technological capabilities struggle to participate in computerized learning; this gap is visible across countries and between wage levels within countries. According to OECD data, only 34% of students in Indonesia have access to a PC for homework purposes, compared to 95% of students in Switzerland, Norway, and Austria.

C. Is web learning just as effective?

There is evidence that studying online can be more compelling in a variety of ways for those who truly approach the proper innovation. According to some research, students generally retain 25–60% more information when learning online compared to merely 8–10% in a traditional classroom. This is primarily due to the students' ability to learn faster online; e-learning requires 40–60% less time investment to learn than in a traditional homeroom setting because students can learn at their own pace, returning to and again reading, skipping, or moving quickly through ideas as they choose. In any case, different age groups have varying opinions on how effective online learning is. There is wide agreement that children, especially younger ones, require a structured environment since they are more easily led astray than adults. According to Dowson Tong, Senior Executive Vice President of Tencent and President of its Cloud and Smart Industries Group, in order to fully benefit from web-based learning, there should be a deliberate effort to give this design and go beyond replicating an actual class or address through video capabilities. Dowson Tong suggests using a variety of cooperation tools and commitment techniques that advance "incorporation, personalization, and insight."

D. Modifying fundamental education:

Without a doubt, this pandemic has caused irreversible damage to a school system that many believe was starting to lose its significance at the time. In his book *21 Lessons for the 21st Century*, researcher Yuval Noah Harari explains how schools still prioritise traditional academic abilities and repetitious learning over more future-relevant competencies like flexibility and judgement. Could the shift to online or web-based learning ever serve as the motivation for creating a fresh, more successful method of learner instruction? After witnessing the advantages personally, some people want to

incorporate e-advancing into their "new reality," but others fear that the quick idea of the transfer online may have prevented this aim.

VIII. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SPREADING INFORMATION IS FEATURED THROUGH COVID-19

Numerous times, major world events serve as a turning point for rapid development; the rise of online commerce after SARS provides an apparent example. It's still unclear to us if this will apply to e-learning beyond COVID-19, but it's one of the few fields where business is still going strong. The need of imparting knowledge across boundaries, institutions, and all segments of society has been made clear by this pandemic. We should all look at the full potential of web learning technology if it can play a role in this situation.

Schools were closed and classes were moved to students' homes in 2020 as the Covid-19 pandemic spread over the world. As a result, several countries faced the challenge of an unexpected and accelerated shift to online learning. This addresses a crucial opportunity to consider innovation, instructional strategy, and education. Computerized technology played a significant role in enabling teachers to instruct students remotely using tools that enabled both simultaneous and nonconcurrent communication with the entire class, groups, and individual children or youngsters; access to learning materials; and intuitive and cooperative exercises. This exceptional issue examines how communities as a whole responded, the upcoming possible opportunities and considerations, and what we may learn moving forward for the modern task of creativity in training during an emergency. While different countries have different COVID-19 disease rates, as of right now, the pandemic has affected more than 1.2 billion children in 186 different countries.

Some are wondering if the popularity of web-based learning will continue to grow after the pandemic and what this would mean for the entire training which has given the unexpected shift away from the study hall in many parts of the world.

A. How can the education answer COVID-19?

Numerous online learning platforms are opening up access to their services due to the high demand for them, including BYJU'S, the most highly regarded education technology company in the world and a Bangalore-based educational technology and online mentoring enterprise founded in 2011. Since reporting free live classes on its Think and Learn application, BYJU's has seen a 200% increment in the quantity of new understudies utilizing its item, as per Mrinal Mohit, the organization's Chief Operating Officer.

Tencent homeroom, in the mean-time, has been utilized broadly since mid-February after the Chinese government educated a fourth of a billion full-time understudies to continue their examinations through web-based stages. This came about in the biggest "online development" throughout the entire existence of training with roughly 730,000, or 81%

of K-12 understudies, going to classes by means of the Tencent K-12 Online School in Wuhan.

Various organizations are enhancing their abilities to provide educators and students with a comprehensive resource. For example, Lark, a Singapore-based collaborative suite that ByteDance initially developed as an internal tool to meet its own remarkable growth, began providing instructors and students with unlimited video conferencing time, auto-interpretation capabilities, ongoing co-altering of project work, and astute schedule planning, among other features. Lark quickly scaled up its global server infrastructure and designing capabilities to ensure a reliable network in an emergency.

B. *Advantages of involving web advancements in educating:*

The review results demonstrate that the significant advantages of involving Web advancements in educating include:

- Interaction, correspondence and joint effort
- Knowledge creation
- Ease of purpose and adaptability, and
- Writing and innovation abilities.

Most members accepted that involving Web Technology in schooling, advances in showing helps construct a feeling of local area, expands connection and correspondence among the educator, understudies, and others, and advances coordinated effort and asset sharing. Coming up next are a portion of the remarks by the members:

- "I believe, whenever utilized accurately, they can assist with fostering a superior feeling of network among understudies and instructors and manage the cost of understudies valuable chances to interface and speak with colleagues and Resources all through the world... "
- "They decrease the distance among instructor and students."
- "Students find out about better approaches for joint effort."
- "Students and instructors consider figuring out how to be a more friendly interaction. It's not only the book and yourself; it's cooperative significance making."

Information creation, the majority of participants explained how Web innovations enable students to "become users of information." Web innovations, technologies give students "the option to generate content themselves rather than just listening to lectures," and thus promotes active and student-centered learning in which students have a feeling of ownership over their education. A few participants also observed that Web developments and educational technologies create an environment where a teacher acts as a facilitator of learning rather than a distributor of knowledge.

C. *Usability and adaptability*

33 percent of the participants said that web tools and/or apparatus are easy to use and adaptive. They observed that while some of the traditional course's executive frameworks are overly static, Web devices, tools, and technology alleviate time constraints by providing a more adaptive learning environment that isn't limited by classroom walls.

D. *Some negative sides of online learning*

Web Technology, which Wikipedia defines as the collection of approaches people use in "obtaining new, or altering existing, information, ways of behaving, abilities, values, or inclinations," is significantly changing how we see education, as mentioned in earlier sections of our research. The use of computer-based coaching is now commonplace in all learning environments throughout the world, altering minds and creating new employment for both teachers and students. Understudies are active, motivated, and eager to learn as a result of the synchronization of innovation in the classroom environment. Additionally, they accept greater responsibility for their education (Johnson, Schwab, and Foa, 1999). Individualizing learning, which is seen as an outcome of creativity, increases students' capacity to resolve problems on their own (Viorica-Torii and Carmen, 2013). As a result, instructors are no longer data carriers but rather planners or designers of learning environments (Hairon and Chai, 2017). Their main goal is to organize the elements of effective learning by placing themselves in the heart of students and educational initiatives. However, more recent research has indicated that innovation has a negative impact on the training process (Fried, 2008; Wentworth and Middleton, 2014), particularly in the four areas listed below:

- Disintegration of students' reading, writing, and number-crunching skills, which are the three core skills every student should be able to master; Despite the fact that classroom innovation generally improves students' motivation to complete their tasks (Al-Hariri and Al-Hattami, 2017; Bishop and Verleger, 2013; Clarke and Svanaes, 2014; Haßler, Major, and Hennessy, 2015; Izadpanah and Alavi, 2016 among others), there is still a great deal of dependence on innovation that appears to negatively affect students., Competencies in three abilities that are of uncontested significance to them, to be specific perusing, composing and math. Spitzer (2014) gives a full record of the dangers of embracing innovation in the homeroom and cautions against its likely adverse consequences on understudies' accomplishments. He refers to Literature avowing that penmanship and perusing are hindered by composing and that Information Technology (IT) achieves shallow handling of data. For this, students don't obtain as much useful information from Google Books as they do from physical books and publications. In essence, Carr (2011) accuses technology of making our brains "shallow" and claims that students who read printed texts have higher comprehension and a more solid memory than those who read online. He argues that "the transition from paper to screen doesn't just have an impact on how we explore a piece of writing" (2011, p. 90). It likewise impacts the level of consideration we dedicate to it and the profundity of our submersion in it." Carr attests that the Internet, for example, achieves shallow, quickly flustered perusers, as "When we go on the web, we enter a environment that advances careless perusing, rushed and diverted thinking, and shallow learning," (2011, p. 116). One more illustration of the adverse consequence of innovative gadgets, for example, cell phones, tablets, PCs and workstations on understudies' presentation is brought to us by Strain-Moritz (2016), an accomplished instructor who determines that messaging has harmed understudies'

capacity to compose full sentences, with no discontinuity or abnormal accentuation. Alhusban (2016) likewise specifies that homeroom advancements definitely influence understudies' capacity to compose, outstandingly with regards to spelling and accentuation, syntactic exactness, spelling, editing, decisive reasoning, regard of soundness and linearity. She additionally contends that consistent openness to short structures disables understudies' capacity to sprinkle out exertion recorded as a hard copy and that the short structures that are habitually utilized in messaging makes it overwhelming for them to recognize formal shows of composing from casual ones. Bronowicki, (2014) takes on a comparable perspective, to be specific that understudies have become sluggish due to their weighty, everyday dependence on innovation. The issue is far more atrocious in elementary schools where understudies are overpowered by innovation, particularly cell phones; which at long last leads their utilization of punctuation to be adversely impacted by textese (for example 4ever rather than everlastingly) (van Dijk et al, 2016). Additionally, Granata (2019, passage 1) announces that "Understudies have put down adored soft cover books and supplanted them with cell phones, iPads and other innovation. Children's perusing for joy has dropped immensely throughout recent years, and innovation might be at fault." Taking everything into account, dependence on innovation in showing these subjects implies a plenty of possible dangers. Truth be told, in 1998, Zheng explored the adverse consequences of utilizing mini-computers and arrived at the accompanying resolution: Concern for the adverse consequence of utilizing adding machines, particularly diagramming number crunchers, is genuine. Since mini-computers are by and large mathematical in nature, understudies may not procure strong reasonable comprehension. Their perspective on arithmetic will presumably be more procedural and appropriately, their critical thinking abilities might be restricted. The advancement of their underlying perspective about math could likewise be frustrated. Besides, in light of it [sic.] plan, a number cruncher may convey deceiving data and make disarray in learning documentation (1998, p. 9). Something like 30 years after the fact, definitively in 2012, the UK government reported its aim to boycott mini-computers in grade schools since understudies use them to an extreme (Stacey, 2014). Math and number-crunching are in their most flawless structures, subjects which advance revelation, investigation and decisive reasoning. The utilization of innovation in showing these subjects, but supportive, is an obstruction to the flourishing of understudies' logical thinking, research has demonstrated.

- The degrading effect of technology; dehumanization of education in a variety of contexts and disintegration of the dynamic between teachers and students, while the utilization of innovation has expanded the amount of data showed in a more limited time and has most certainly made understudies ready to imagine this data in a superior manner (for example through PowerPoint Presentations, guides and graphs), the overreliance on innovation in homerooms has a dehumanizing impact. Kemp et al. (2015, p.4) declares that over the course of the past 10 years specifically, "showing has been torn from the domain of

human undertakings and transformed into a mechanical leviathan that is gradually usurping the spirit of the calling." This 'leviathan', a legendary ocean beast as per the Jewish convictions, is accessible in numerous areas and at many degrees of schooling, including pre-bundled educational programs that are not planned by the educator of a specific course. In advanced education establishments and in web-based courses, for example, educators present their illustrations from a far, and understudies are expected to connect with machines, as opposed to with people. A definitive outcome is an educator who is clueless or very little about his/her understudies and understudies showing no cozy relationship with their instructor. Cazan et al (2016); Izadpanah and Alavi (2016) and Nye (2006) among others, have proactively featured the dehumanizing impact of innovation on understudy educator connections. Nye (2006, p, truth be told. 186) contends that Technology "pulls you away from the actual climate. You truly block out the world," and that "The present undergrads are adjusted to a universe of internet contributing to a blog, texting, and Web perusing that leaves electronic follows," (p. 188). Izadpanah and Alavi (2016) concentrated on the mentalities of a gathering of Iranian secondary school understudies towards involving PCs as a medium to work with learning English in study halls. Results gathered from the review show that around 58% of the understudies engaged with the overview accept that utilizing PCs has a dehumanizing impact. Comparative outcomes were found by Cazan et al (2016), who researched the connection between the degree of nervousness among some secondary school and college understudies in Romania, and their PC education. Examination has shown that the higher the students PC self-viability is, the less tension they have in the classroom halls. In a general public like the Romanian one, where admittance to PCs at home is extremely restricted, numerous understudies are supposed to feel restless when they are supposed to deal with computerized gadgets in the study halls. Reliance on innovation in the homerooms likewise involves the absence of compatibility among educators and understudies or potentially among understudies themselves; which prompts dissolving the social connections associated with instructing, in this manner disintegrating one of the fundamental points of schooling (Nneji, 2014). On the off chance that educators rely upon innovation for quite a while in the classrooms, there is not really any time for them to anily affect their students. In similar style, understudies don't have the chance to foster sound associations with each other. Rivedal (2017) alludes to the dehumanizing part of innovation as a "zombie walk" and composes (section 6) that "Our students who are the most separated are normally the ones who are stuck on their telephones and strolling the corridors with their heads down." Wilkins (2014) likewise refers to realities about instructors' and students' perspectives towards the utilization of innovation and its extraordinary impact on understudy educator connections, with some accepting that utilizing innovation hampers the compatibility among instructors and understudies and structures an impediment to simple correspondence between them.

- Students' isolation from any kind of social interaction due to technology and isolation in a computerized and virtual environment. Community and coordinated effort are two distinguishing characteristics of face-to-face instruction, whereas the absence of any sense of cohesion or camaraderie distinguishes innovation-based instruction. Disengagement is characterized by the psychoanalytic theory as a defensive mechanism adopted by the brain when people are imprisoned in circumstances they perceive as unfavourable or compromising. As a result, students who regularly use technology develop a sense of security and well-being while "connected" to their devices, and they start to avoid any social interactions that could cause them to become detached. In 2001, Paul and Brier begat "friend sickness" to allude to the disengagement undergraduates feel while moving to school and abandoning old school kinships. They imagine that innovation overcomes that issue in connections and furnishes those youthful undergraduates with the feeling that those kinships have not disappeared. Innovation helps Technology covers people in the virtual world, entraps them and achieves a sensation of seclusion. Lee (2009, p. 510) points out the risk of innovation improved disengagement and the compromising effect it might have on the kids' social turn of events, contending that the perception that a PC is put in a singular's room as opposed to a family room and that a kid utilizes a PC alone with practically no other relatives' presence enhances worries about friendly confinement and unsafe impacts on youngsters' social advancement Turkle (2011) focuses to the dichotomous impact of innovation when it tears its client between the illusive impression of organization, from one viewpoint, and the unpleasant truth of separation, on the other. She specifies (p. 280): "On the web, we effectively find 'organization', yet are depleted by the tension of execution. We appreciate nonstop association however seldom stand out." as a matter of fact, and especially in virtual or distance learning, undergraduates' associations with their educators and partners are exceptionally feeble; which might achieve a sensation of seclusion and hamper undergraduates' requirement for cooperation (Croft et al, 2010). In the UK alone, for example, 13 colleges have distance learning programs permitting in excess of 1500 Master's program undergraduates to study by means of the Internet. Albeit these undergraduates are upheld in numerous ways, through intuitive tasks, custom fitted help and online discussions, they don't approach the local area of undergraduates living nearby; which makes a feeling of dejection (Vonberg, 2015). This sensation of separation frequently brings about a sensation of forlornness and is extraordinarily connected with the dehumanizing impact of innovation. The two issues include the disregard of human relations in the instructive field and focus on exhaustive reliance on innovation. Educators rely upon innovative gadgets to instruct and undergraduates are denied of any type of social cooperation. Is seriously disturbing that disconnection is increasingly more predominant among youthful undergraduates who, across the world, go to schools where the utilization of tablets is typical. Karsenti and Fievez (2013) summon the instance of Quebec kids being diverted because of the over the top dependence on tablets in learning. Iserbyt et al (2014)

demand that the redundant utilization of innovation based games and diversion, in a bid to deliver the illustrations really engaging, involves undergraduates' confinement, and could at long last prompt more unfortunate results of learning. Interruption can likewise be added to the specialized issues going with the utilization of tablets by youthful undergraduates, even on account of finishing straightforward jobs, for example, hole filling and coordinating, particularly on the off chance that there is no specialized help accessible to manage those issues in a brief manner (Culén and Gasparini, 2012). Besides, the coming of cell phones has prompted a quantum jump in the mix of ICT in training. Cell phones are currently generally utilized in numerous region all over the planet. Upheld by an enormous number of instructive applications, Smartphones are viewed as a promising method of teaching, especially at the higher-instructive level (El-Hussein and Cronje, 2010). At the moment, cell phones are seen as tools for communicating and exchanging information (Kearney et al, 2012). However, studies have shown that the widespread use of cell phones in the classroom causes attention disruption, information fragmentation, and a failure on the part of teachers to supervise homerooms (Ad and Göktaş, 2014). Therefore, it seems that students' use of technology has resulted in their disengagement and depression because they frequently forget there are friends they can rely on and connect with because they are so engaged in operating the classroom computers.

- The increase of social disparities between the wealthy and the poor, which are demonstrated by students who have access to technology and those who do not, technological advancements, and the social class divide, is another negative aspect of the reliance on innovation in education. This is due to the enormous gap that innovation creates between the wealthy and the poor. Massive differences between developed and developing countries are very obvious in school systems. Schools in developed countries receive virtually all mechanical equipment (PCs, workstations, tablets, projectors, and Internet connectivity), whereas those in agricultural countries largely lack these resources. In this way, students in developing countries graduate with a limited set of essential mechanical skills (for example, a limited understanding of computers) and have enormous challenges finding well-paying employment or find it too difficult to even consider competing in the global market. According to van Dijk and Hacker (2011), there is often a digital division between students from different social backgrounds. This is true even in developed countries. Unlucky students may use technology in their classes, but they are unable to afford any equipment at home. This is seen in how poorly these students perform academically when compared to their wealthy friends. Knowing this population from my work [at Porterville Adult School], I have discovered that a significant portion of the students we serve, especially those who speak English as a second language, are computer illiterate and, as a result, fall on the lean side of the spectrum (Steele-Carlin, 2017). If this is the result of the technological divide in the US, it should be much worse in other countries where the divide is wider, like in Egypt, where tuition-based schools and colleges have a good, functional mechanical

climate in comparison to state schools and colleges, which is reflected in the significantly different degrees of graduates from the two types of training (Warschauer, 2011). Although the Egyptian government has provided access to the Internet and cutting-edge technology in many of its schools, these resources are not being used because of the excessive formality or lack of training provided to teachers. Most Egyptians can't bring themselves to buy any mechanical devices or novel software at home, therefore most graduates of state educational institutions fall short on crucial PC skills and require extensive recovery once they graduate. It seems to reason that the digital gap would encourage aloof behavior because the innovation might give students a feeling of being persecuted and failing their academics.

E. Best practices and ways to educate with web advances

These days, the utilization of innovation in schooling is unavoidable. Present day mechanical gadgets have known tremendous development from one side of the world to the other, prompting significant changes in the manner in which students learn and educators educate. Regularly, the level of outcome of an instructive establishment is estimated against how much innovation that is being coordinated in its classrooms. Technology in this manner has so far had a significant stake in student's social and instructive lives; which clearly raises a warmed worry about the impacts of its utilization. A small number of scientists are currently interested in the impact of innovation on students' lives and working to limit the drastic effects that these classroom devices are having on students' mentalities and ways of acting. While this is going on, nobody denies the fact that it is very impossible to eliminate innovation from the classroom setting. However, at this time, our focus is on limiting its negative effects.

UNICEF (2017, p. 122) suggested that users of technology is to "Harness the good" and "limit the harm.". They shared a list of recommendations on how to deal, manage technology in such a way that it would not be threatening and harmful to learners. The suggestions carries,

- To ensure that students connect with one another even when fully immersed in a digital environment,
- To design, plan, and oversee events that inevitably encourage collaboration and communication,
- To inspire tech-savvy students to create interactive content that would enhance their learning, experience, and course. • To share and compare (blog posts, classroom projects, etc.) to see how technology can connect learners/students all over the world.
- To enable knowledgeable students to develop insightful assignments that will enhance the courses.

Instructor preparing may likewise be another springboard whereon to stand while trying to ensure the suitable utilization of innovation. As a matter of fact, the additional preparation educators get, the better way innovation would be utilized and the more positive impacts it would involve. Laurillard (2002) contends that to be successful, innovation-based gadgets wouldn't be compelling except if their utilization is joined by fitting instructive methodologies. Essentially, McFarlane (1997) learns that

embedding innovation in showing won't have the normal added esteem except if targets are plainly set and assignments are all around planned. In addition, school systems are presently expected to guarantee that coordinating ICT programs in the educational plan ought to be upheld by powerful Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programs for teachers wherein innovation-based learning is consolidated. Guardians ought to likewise be made mindful that innovation isn't a gift constantly, and that it is presently their own need to outfit areas of strength for that among their off springs to utilize innovation all over and whenever. Innovation isn't static. It continually changes, acquiring new gadgets and sending others to oldness. Taking this part of innovation in thought includes staying aware of that speed and adjusting teaching method to innovation, accordingly outfitting obstructions and expanding benefits.

- As referenced before, the members in this study were asked the way that they have utilized Web 2.0 advancements. In their educating, what educational procedures or strategies have functioned admirably, and what has not worked for them. In light of information examinations, the accompanying prescribed procedures or rules were recognized.
- Avoid introducing pupils to so many unique advancements in a single semester. various people. That teachers add more instruments while using less only when skill is developed.
- Avoid using many innovations that perform the same function. Several participants suggested that teachers
- Should not display more than one application that performs the same function. Students should take note because of this regularly.
- Manage a few email records and gatherings and another innovation, whenever utilized like a current device, basically makes Management issues. Understudies and I likewise felt on occasion that Wiki space is simply one more discussion to oversee notwithstanding a few Email accounts, WebCT, and so on in this bustling life. The way that the greater part of my studentss were working all day and had a few email accounts and other "online message sheets" to check added to that inclination, maybe.
- Provide guidance, instructional exercises, models, and successive input.
- Facilitate cooperative learning. The members in this study revealed different procedures for Facilitating cooperative picking up utilizing Web 2.0 advancements. Instances of the methodologies incorporate the accompanying: Using wikis for cooperative composing projects, involving a blog as a cooperative reflection space past private diaries by expecting understudies to answer and give criticism to one another, Using a social bookmarking webpage for sharing assets, Using peer assessment. Construct a feeling of local area in your study hall first prior to attempting more open coordinated effort. Web 2.0 is Generally portrayed by transparency, social communication and coordinated effort. As one might anticipate, some of the participants used Web 2.0 tools for inter-institutional coordination. One said that her students collaborated with students from another college to create a wiki-book on learning theories. Given that the students entrance level knowledge and concentrate (research versus practice) were distinct, it is agreed that

their inter-institutional coordinated effort was not particularly fruitful.

- The members also advocated creating an inviting and supportive environment and setting clear objectives and targets for using Web 2.0 innovations in instruction.
- Rewarding students for good work and great commitments, and showing YouTube recordings to begin or end class.

IX. CONCLUSION

Technology has steadily transformed the fundamental nature of teaching and learning over the past few years or so, tracking its path to the study hall. Today, it's thought that innovation is one of the most important skills that pupils should possess for the twenty-first century. Access to several knowledge sources is a key component of another education. This initiative to coordinate innovation in the classroom setting won't ever come to an end, whether it's for the better or worse, and each advancement will encourage another really interesting project.

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- **Availability of data and materials:** (Table.1. EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY AND EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITY DURING COVID-19 SCHOOL CLOSURES: A CASE STUDY OF CHENNAI, TAMIL NADU), Fig.1, Fig.2, Fig.3, Source: February 2021 Brookings phone surveys.
- **Authors' contributions:** Editing, Research Methods, Observation, Data collection, etc.

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